

Mechanistic insights into G protein association with a G protein-coupled receptor

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Abstract

G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) activate heterotrimeric G proteins by promoting guanine nucleotide exchange. Here, we investigate the process of functional association between G proteins and GPCRs and describe the events that ultimately lead to the ejection of GDP from its binding pocket in the $G\alpha$ subunit. In atomic detail, we reveal the temporal progression of structural rearrangements of GDP-bound heterotrimeric Gs protein (GsGDP) upon coupling to the β 2-adrenergic receptor (β 2AR) using molecular dynamics simulations. The binding of GsGDP to the β 2AR is followed by long-range allosteric effects that significantly reduce the energy needed for GDP release, the rate-limiting step during G-protein activation. In particular, the opening of α 1- α F helices, displacement of the α G helix, and the opening of the α -helical domain weaken the interaction between GDP and the G protein. Signal transduction to the G protein occurs via a novel receptor interface, confirmed by site-directed mutagenesis and functional assays. From this β 2AR-GsGDP intermediate, the G protein must undergo an in-plane rotation along the receptor axis to reach the β 2AR-Gempty state. The simulations shed light on how the structural elements at the receptor-G-protein interface interact to transmit the signal over 30Å to the nucleotide-binding site. Our analysis extends the current limited view of nucleotide-free snapshots to include additional states and structural features responsible for signaling and G protein coupling specificity.

Introduction

Heterotrimeric G proteins ($G\alpha\beta\gamma$) are guanine nucleotide-binding proteins consisting of alpha (α), beta (β), and gamma (γ) subunits. G proteins are activated by G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs), the largest family of membrane receptors sharing a common seven transmembrane helix (TM) structure¹. Receptor-mediated G-protein activation plays a key role in various physiological processes, and almost one-third of all medical drugs aim to modulate GPCR signaling². The biochemical and biophysical basis of GPCR signaling has been studied for many decades, revealing essential insights into signal transfer at the molecular level. Structural investigations showed that for most GPCRs, upon extracellular ligand binding, the 7-TM bundle undergoes a conformational change that opens up an intracellular pocket to which the C-terminal α 5 helix of the $G\alpha$ -subunit can bind^{3,4,5}. Upon coupling to the receptor, the α 5 helix, undergoes a conformational change that propagates to the nucleotide-binding pocket, which lies between the Ras-homology domain (Ras) and the α -helical domain (AHD), and eventually leads to GDP release⁵. The most striking structural change accompanying the release of GDP is a major displacement of the AHD relative to the Ras that opens up the nucleotide-binding pocket. Similar structural changes are found in different nucleotide-free R-G^{empty} complexes, suggesting an overall conserved signal transduction mechanism^{6,7,8}. However, structural snapshots of the reaction's beginning and end cannot infer the temporal sequence of events leading to nucleotide exchange^{9,10}. In fact, the functional association of G^{GDP} with an agonist-bound receptor leads to the formation of R-G^{GDP} intermediates before GDP is released^{10,11,12,13,14,15} (**Figure 1**). Although R-G^{GDP} intermediates are thought to play an important, if not crucial, role in the selective binding of G proteins to receptors, little is known about their formation and structure^{10,16,17,18,19,20,21}.

In the present study, with an aim to understand the process of receptor-mediated G-protein activation, we investigate the first steps of this reaction sequence for the β_2 -adrenoceptor-Gs (β_2 AR-Gs) signaling system, for which there is a wealth of experimental data that can expand further interpretation^{5,10,16,22,23,24,25}. The β_2 AR is a family A GPCR that primarily couples to Gs to enhance intracellular cAMP levels²⁶, hence regulating important physiological responses such as smooth muscle relaxation and bronchodilation²⁷. A recent analysis of hydrogen-deuterium exchange and radio-footprint labeling data suggests that β_2 AR-mediated Gs protein activation passes through several intermediate conformations before GDP is released¹⁰. Moreover, this analysis indicates that the R-G^{empty} structures obtained after prolonged incubation in the presence of apyrase, which hydrolyzes free nucleotides, are not representative of this intermediate, which is short-lived at physiological concentrations of GDP and GTP (36 μ M and 305 μ M in humans, respectively)¹⁰.

We used all-atom molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to investigate the coupling of membrane-anchored Gs^{GDP} to a membrane-embedded β_2 AR¹⁶ bound to a high-affinity agonist. We identify an extended binding interface between β_2 AR and Gs^{GDP} that differs from that observed in the β_2 AR-Gs^{empty} complex. This interface which involves intracellular loop 1 (ICL1), transmembrane helix 2 (TM2), and helix 8 (H8), is confirmed by site-directed mutagenesis and functional assays. In addition, we observe substantial conformational changes at the nucleotide-binding pocket that significantly reduce the energy needed for GDP release. The simulations suggest that lowering binding affinity and subsequent release of GDP are accompanied by structural changes at the receptor-G-protein interface and a rotational movement of the G protein relative to the receptor (**Figure 1**). Our analysis sheds new light on the hitherto structurally unknown initial steps of receptor-mediated G-protein activation and provides insights into the mechanism of receptor-Gs protein coupling specificity.

Results

Gs associates with β_2 AR via a new coupling interface

In the starting model (**Methods**), we placed Gs^{GDP} and β_2 AR sufficiently far from each other (Figure 2A, left inset) to avoid imposing intramolecular contacts between both proteins while allowing for free fluctuation and spontaneous recognition, and ran four independent replicas of 8 μ s (for a list of MD simulations, see Table S1). The initial orientation of Gs^{GDP} with respect to β_2 AR was based on a recent crystal structure of the β_2 AR ligated to a 14-mer-peptide derived from the C-terminus of α_5 ¹⁶, where we provided the first hint for an alternative engagement of α_5 with the receptor in a putative β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} intermediate. Thus, in our model, α_5 is rotated counterclockwise with respect to its position in β_2 AR-Gs^{empty} and oriented towards the receptor in such a way that binding of the C-terminal residue E392 ^{α_5} to the conserved β_2 AR residue R131^{3,50}, in the TM3 D(E)RY motif, is possible even without further rearrangements of the G protein (**Figure 2A, insets, Extended Data Fig 1**). Moreover, in the receptor-free

Gs^{GDP} structure¹⁶, E392^{α5} is solvent-exposed and thus directly available for interaction with the β₂AR, whereas the neighboring residue Y391^{α5}, which interacts with R131^{3.50} of the receptor in the β₂AR-Gs^{empty} complex⁵, is still completely buried at the interface between α5 and the αN-β1 junction (**Extended Data Fig 1A1**). Finally, as in the crystal structure of the β₂AR complexed with a G-protein mimicking nanobody²⁸, we started our simulations with an intact D130^{3.49}-R131^{3.50} side chain interaction, in which the side chain of R131^{3.50} is held toward the G protein by D130^{3.49} to facilitate binding to the carboxyl-terminus L394^{α5}. Provided the G protein binds β₂AR following the former parameters, our initial arrangement should enhance complex formation.

In this first set of simulations (**Table S 1**), Gs^{GDP} associates almost instantaneously with the β₂AR (**movie 1, Figure 2A,B**). Closer examination reveals that Gs^{GDP} association with the receptor is controlled by reorganization and establishment of polar interactions at the binding interface, indicating that the two binding partners align along electrostatically compatible surfaces. The α5 helix, essential for the recognition and selective binding of G proteins to receptors^{29,30,31,32,33}, plays a major role in this binding process (**Table S 2A**). In all simulations, we observe progressive binding of α5 to the receptor, while the nearby αN helix retains a dynamic interaction with H8 and ICL1 of the receptor (**movie 1**). Notably, the α5 C-terminus is guided into its binding pocket by three lysines at the cytoplasmic end of TM6 (**Figure 2E, movie 1**). The α5 C-terminal residues L394^{α5} and E392^{α5} control the progression through such 'lysine ladder', which induces a rotameric switch of R131^{3.50} that eventually breaks the D130^{3.49}-R131^{3.50} ionic interaction (**movie 1**). The disruption of this interaction is consistent with previous structural and biophysical analyses of rhodopsin activation^{4,34} and is also observed in nucleotide-free complex structures of rhodopsin with Gt³⁵ and the β₂AR with Gs⁵. Interestingly, the E392^{α5}-R131^{3.50} bridge, one of the key interactions of the β₂AR-α5-peptide structure¹⁶, forms very early and then persists in all simulations, suggesting a key role in the process of Gs^{GDP} association with the β₂AR (**movie 1, Figure 2A,B**). Consistent with this, mutation of E392^{α5} significantly reduces receptor-mediated G-protein activation with β₂AR¹⁶.

In this novel binding mode and orientation of α5, the G-protein interface in the β₂AR-Gs^{GDP} simulations is rotated counterclockwise (as viewed from the cytoplasm) by about 40° towards H8 and intracellular loop 1 (ICL1), compared to β₂AR-Gs^{empty} (**Figure 3A**). In the β₂AR-Gs^{GDP} simulations, αN is located at H8 and ICL1 (**Figure 3A**). In contrast, in β₂AR-Gs^{empty}, the αN moves away and interacts exclusively with ICL2 (**Figure 3A**). As in β₂AR-Gs^{empty} (**see Table S 1**), α5 accounts for the most contacts in the simulations of β₂AR-Gs^{GDP} with the receptor (**Table S 2C**). The α5 helix is, however, more vertically tilted and occupies a more central position within the G-protein binding pocket in β₂AR-Gs^{GDP} (**Figure 3A**). A different binding mode of G^{GDP} to the receptor was expected, as α5 binding is sterically hindered in an orientation similar to R-G^{empty} (see in ref⁴ Fig. 5 and¹²). Consequently, compared to β₂AR-Gs^{empty}, which predominantly

forms lateral contacts with TM3-7 and ICL2 (ICL3 is not resolved), $\alpha 5$ interacts with H8, TM2 and ICL1 in the simulations of $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$.

Moreover, αN forms an extended interface with H8 and ICL1, which account for about 20% of the receptor contacts with the G protein (**Table S 2C**). In contrast, in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ crystal structure, only a single and weak contact is formed between $\text{A39}^{\alpha\text{N}}$ with $\text{S143}^{\text{ICL2}}$ and not with H8⁵. The extended interface of αN with the receptor in our simulations of $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ agrees with previous crosslinking experiments, ¹⁹F nuclear Overhauser effects and mutational analysis of $\text{G}_t\alpha\text{N}$ ^{36,37,38}. Moreover, the extended interface of αN with the receptor specifically involves the last two turns of the helix upstream of the $\beta 1$ -sheet (αN - $\beta 1$ junction) (**Table S 2A,B,C**), whose deletion had the greatest effect on light-induced signal transduction of G_t ³⁹. Finally, H8 engagement could contribute to the decrease in H8 hydrogen-deuterium-exchange upon $\beta_2\text{AR}$ coupling to Gs ¹⁰, an interaction not observed in the crystal $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ structure. In conclusion, in the simulations leading to an initial $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ complex, almost all intracellular structural elements of the receptor are involved in G-protein binding and are compatible with existing experimental observations^{22,10}.

We used site-directed mutagenesis to experimentally test the functional significance of the newly detected receptor interface. During the association process, $\alpha 5$ 'climbs' TM6 and binds to residues deep in the intracellular binding pocket of the receptor (Figure 2E). Basic amino acids $\text{K270}^{6.32}$ and $\text{K273}^{6.35}$ form the final 'rungs' of the lysine ladder at the cytoplasmic end of TM6 and guide $\alpha 5$ binding in the pocket (Figure 2E, **Extended Data Fig 5**). Furthermore, $\text{K273}^{6.35}$ does not participate in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ complex. Accordingly, we expected that a $\text{K270Q}^{6.32}$ and $\text{K273Q}^{6.35}$ double mutation would strongly affect Gs protein association and activation. Finally, $\text{Y391}^{\alpha 5}$ binds to $\text{N69}^{2.40}$ of TM2 deep in the G-protein binding pocket of the receptor when the interaction between $\alpha 5$ and the αN - $\beta 1$ junction opens up during the association process, releasing $\text{Y391}^{\alpha 5}$ and $\text{H387}^{\alpha 5}$ from their buried (**Extended Data Fig 1A1**) positions in inactive Gs^{GDP} (**Figure 4E**). In this binding mode, $\text{H387}^{\alpha 5}$ interacts with R63^{ICL1} of the receptor. Since neither $\text{N69}^{2.40}$ nor R63^{ICL1} are part of the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ interface (Figure 3A, **Extended Data Fig 7B**), we mutated both residues to verify the binding mode observed in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ complex. Consistent with our assumptions, a strong effect of $\text{K270Q}^{6.32}/\text{K273Q}^{6.35}$ and $\text{R63Q}^{\text{ICL1}}/\text{N69M}^{2.40}$ on Gs activation of adenylyl cyclase is observed, without affecting receptor-ligand affinity, providing evidence that the observed decrease in EC_{50} of G-protein activation is due in part to disruption of complex formation and not deactivation of the receptor (Figure 3B-C, **Extended Data Fig 8A-B**). Note also that the functional effect of the $\text{K270Q}^{6.32}/\text{K273Q}^{6.35}$ mutations could be partly due to the reduced cell-surface expression levels.

GDP destabilization in response to receptor association

Since the association of Gs^{GDP} with the β_2 AR is almost instantaneous, we were able to examine potential long-range allosteric effects as the simulations progressed (Figure 2C, D, **Extended Data Fig 2**, Table S 4). To assess the effect of the receptor on GDP unbinding, we ran another set of four independent 8- μ s-long MD simulations of Gs^{GDP} without the receptor for comparison (Table S 1). These simulations show the activity and dynamics of Gs^{GDP} alone in the same time window and serve as a baseline comparison to the β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} simulations. Consistent with the low basal activity¹⁰ of Gs^{GDP}, we see no alterations in the GDP-binding pocket in the control simulations (Figure 2C-D, **Extended Data Fig 2**, black lines, **movie 2**), where the nucleotide remains tightly sandwiched between the AHD and Ras of G α . In these Gs^{GDP} simulations, the α , β -phosphates, and the pentose sugar ribose are held in position by interactions with prominent structural elements in G α such as switchI, α D, α E, α dae, α F, α G, β 3, β 5, P-loop, TCAT and Mg²⁺, tightly fixing the nucleotide in its binding pocket (**Figure 4B**, **Extended Data Fig 2**, **movie 3**).

In contrast, in the β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} simulations, we observe distinct structural changes in the GDP-binding pocket, indicated by a significant increase in GDP solvent accessibility (**Extended Data Fig 2B**). Strikingly, in all trajectories, we observe disruptions of the GDP-R201^{SwitchI} and the E50^{Ploop}-R201^{SwitchI} interactions, whereas both contacts remain fully formed in simulations of Gs^{GDP} (Figure 2C-D, **Extended Data Fig 2A**, black lines). Disruption of the GDP-R201^{SwitchI} and the E50^{Ploop}-R201^{SwitchI} salt-bridge is suggested to be a necessary and rate-limiting step for GDP release^{40,41} but previously unobserved, even in exceptionally long MD simulations of Gi^{GDP} without the receptor⁴². Interestingly, in the trajectory with the most prominent disruption, we observe additional massive structural changes in G α (**Extended Data Fig 2**, **movie 2**, **movie 3**): The Ras- α 1 and AHD- α F interaction breaks and the AHD and Ras- α G move as rigid-bodies in opposing directions away from GDP, exposing these structural elements and major parts of GDP to the solvent (**Extended Data Fig 2B**), in agreement with pulse-labeling hydrogen-deuterium-exchange profiles¹⁰. This ‘butterfly-like’ opening of the nucleotide-binding pocket massively rearranges the network of interactions that holds the nucleotide in position (Figure 4B-C, **movie 2**, **movie 3**). While the β -phosphate remains fixed to G α , mainly by the P-loop and β 3, which prevent total GDP release, the α -phosphate breaks contacts with switchI, α D, α E, α dae, α F, α G, and C365^{TCAT} and A366^{TCAT}, allowing for a flip of the pentose sugar ribose and the α -phosphate (Figure 4C,F).

To separate our bulk data, comprising 64 μ s of simulations in total, into states representing Gs^{GDP} conformations with different structural properties, we combined the two datasets of Gs^{GDP} and β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} simulations and analyzed them in terms of the principal components^{43,44} of Gs^{GDP} motion (**Extended Data Fig 3**, Methods). A state in which the AHD is closed and the α 5-helix is bent toward the G α -Ras domain as it is in the inactive structure¹⁶, is only observed in the absence of the receptor (**Figure 4A-B**, **orange**). Next, we find ensembles (**Figure 4A**, **magenta and cyan**) common to both sets of simulations, Gs^{GDP} and β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP}, in which the AHD of the G protein is still closed, but the α 5-helix already straightening out (**Extended Data Fig 3C,D**). Finally, we observe a state that occurs only in the presence of the receptor (**Figure 4A**, **purple**). In this state, where α 5 reaches a maximum of contacts with

the receptor (**Table S 7**), we observe additional rigid-body motions in $G\alpha$, most notably opening of the AHD and displacement of αG , associated with breaking GDP contacts (**Figure 4A-F, Table S 6**). We named this state, which persists in a simulation extended to 30 μs (**Table S 1, Extended Data Fig 3E**), β_2AR-Gs^{GDP} intermediate. A rough estimate of the energy needed for GDP release (**Table S 5**) shows that the receptor nearly halves this energy in this state, implying that the receptor boosts the GDP-release reaction constant by several orders of magnitude in the β_2AR-Gs^{GDP} intermediate.

The restructuring of amino acids (**Extended Data Fig 6A,B**) in Gs^{GDP} upon association with the receptor provides potential clues to pathways by which the signal is transmitted from the receptor to the nucleotide binding pocket. Our contact analysis suggests two pathways centered on $\alpha 5$. In the first pathway, dynamic binding of the ICL1 between the $\alpha 5$ and the $\alpha N-\beta 1$ junction rearranges a network of aromatic residues linking $\alpha 5$ to $\beta 1-3$ (**movie 1, Figure 4E, Extended Data Fig 7**). This rearrangement propagates the signal from the receptor to Ras- $\alpha 1$ and AHD- αF near the nucleotide-binding pocket, disrupting the GDP-R201^{SwitchI} and the E50^{Loop}-R201^{SwitchI} interactions and exposing GDP to the solvent (**Extended Data Fig 2B**). In the trajectory leading to the massive structural changes of $G\alpha$ in the β_2AR-Gs^{GDP} intermediate, all initial interactions between Ras- $\alpha 1$ and AHD- αF break (**Extended Data Fig 2C, Figure 4F, left**). In this trajectory, a secondary signal transduction pathway appears to become established via ICL2, which is α -helical in the β_2AR-Gs^{GDP} intermediate (**Extended Data Fig 3H, Extended Data Fig 4**) and couples $\beta 6$ to $\alpha 5$ through an extended network of polar and π - π interactions (**Figure 4D, right, Extended Data Fig 4C**). Subtle shifts in the interactions between $\beta 6$, TCAT and $\beta 5$ residues appear to transmit the signal to the nucleotide-binding pocket breaking the backbone hydrogen bonding interaction of the adjacent T364^{TCAT} with K293 ^{$\beta 5-\alpha G$} (**Extended Data Fig 6**) and leading to an outward shift of αG and with it $\alpha 4$ (**Figure 4F middle, Extended Data Fig 7**). These structural changes finally break the K293 ^{$\beta 5-\alpha G$} -D173 ^{$\alpha D-\alpha E$} lock (**Extended Data Fig 3D, Extended Data Fig 6**) releasing the AHD from the Ras (**Figure 4F, right**), and disrupting the remaining network of interactions holding the α -phosphate and the ribose of GDP (**Figure 4C**).

Role of TM6 and ICL2 conformation for Gs coupling

To reach the β_2AR-Gs^{GDP} intermediate, the receptor undergoes several noticeable conformational changes, particularly at TM6 and ICL2 (**Figure 4D**). Both structural elements of the receptor, which also contribute most of the contacts to interface with the G protein (**Table S 7, Table S 2B**), are thought to play a role in Gs coupling specificity^{31,45}. The ability to accommodate the bulky $\alpha 5$ C-terminus of Gas (or G αq) with the two large amino acid residues E392 ^{$\alpha 5$} and Y391 ^{$\alpha 5$} had previously been assessed as a prerequisite for receptors to be able to drive these signaling pathways^{31,35,46,47}. Moreover, NMR experiments showed that Gs but not Gi binding promotes the formation of an α -helix within ICL2, arguing for a functional role of the ICL2 conformation for Gs coupling⁴⁵. In the β_2AR-Gs^{GDP} intermediate, the cytoplasmic half of TM6 kinks outward at a Glycine-rich motif near the center of the helix⁴⁸ (**Figure 2E, last cartoon, Figure 4D**) to adapt to the bulky moieties of E392 ^{$\alpha 5$} and Y391 ^{$\alpha 5$} . The kink arises initially

when the backbone-backbone interaction at the α -helical turn between I277^{6.39} and T281^{6.43} breaks, and it can be stabilized by Y326^{7.53} from the NPxxY motif⁴⁹ interacting with I277^{6.39} and G280^{6.42} (**movie 1, Figure 4**). With this, $\alpha 5$ is then able to form interactions with the last rung of the lysine ladder, K273^{6.32} (**Figure 2**), establishing the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (**Extended Data Fig 5**). Comparison with other family A receptors shows that Glycine at position G280^{6.42} is significantly overrepresented in receptors that couple to Gs, while Glycine at position G276^{6.38} can be substituted by small amino acids Ala, Ser and Thr in Gs that may still permit local flexibility. This conservation analysis suggests a generalizable Gs recognition mechanism by a large TM6 outward tilt (**Table S 3 C**).

Recently, a study based on the evolutionary history of GPCRs, proposed the existence of a so-called selectivity barcode, *i.e.*, patterns of amino acids on the different G proteins recognized by receptors^{6,30}. In the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate, the ICL2 adopts an α -helical conformation stabilized by a network of polar and aromatic interactions mainly with barcode residues from $\alpha 5$ and $\beta 6$ of G α (Figure 4D, right). Specifically, Q142^{ICL2} and Y141^{ICL2} interact with R385 ^{$\alpha 5$} and D381 ^{$\alpha 5$} , and F139^{ICL2} interacts with Y360 ^{$\beta 6$} and H362 ^{$\beta 6$} (Extended Data Fig 4). The former interactions hold $\alpha 5$ in position laterally, while the latter interaction establishes the connection of $\alpha 5$ with $\beta 6$ across ICL2 (Figure 4D, right), thereby transmitting the signal to GDP (Extended Data Fig 7, Extended Data Fig 4G, Extended Data Fig 6). Of the amino acids involved, F139^{ICL2} has already been shown as crucial for G-protein activation in $\beta_2\text{AR}$ by previous mutational and functional analysis^{5,10}. To further assess the impact of the ICL2 for nucleotide exchange, we selected the two residues Y141^{ICL2} and Q142^{ICL2} that show only weak interactions with Gs⁴⁵ in $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ for further site-directed mutagenesis experiments. Consistent with the proposed functional role of the two residues, Y141V^{ICL2} and Q142L^{ICL2} showed a marked reduction of EC₅₀ of G-protein activation without affecting receptor-ligand affinity (Figure 3B).

Following these notions, we carried out a new set of independent 8- μs -long MD simulations starting from the early frames of the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ simulations, in which the TM6 is already kinked, allowing the carboxyl-terminus of $\alpha 5$ to climb the last rung of the lysine-ladder, and the ICL2 $\alpha 5$ - $\beta 6$ interface to form (Table S 1, **Methods**, Extended Data Fig 6B). In these frames, the GDP-R201^{SwitchI} and the E50^{Loop}-R201^{SwitchI} salt-bridge are not yet broken, and GDP is not yet exposed to the solvent. In the resulting simulations, we again observe a significant increase in solvent exposure of GDP (Extended Data Fig 6C), which, in the majority of simulations, is followed by major structural changes in G α (**Extended Data Fig 3 F3-5**). In addition to the intermediate state observed in the initial set of MD simulations, we observe a new $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate that becomes fully established after 10 μs in a 20- μs -long trajectory (**Extended Data Fig 3E, F5, movie 4**). This state exhibits all structural features of a functional GDP-bound intermediate, such as the opening of $\alpha 1$ - αF , displacement of αG and opening of the α -helical domain breaking GDP contacts, but with a different orientation of the AHD (**Figure 4F, Extended Data Fig 3F**). In the respective trajectory, both signaling pathways are switched-on early, likely due to suitable TM6 and ICL2 starting conformations (Extended Data Fig 6).

Our observations suggest a broad energy landscape with multiple GDP-bound intermediate states (**Extended Data Fig 3**) visited on the way to nucleotide release. These intermediates likely provide similar, but not identical, routes to release GDP and eventually reach the nucleotide-free state. In $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$, the ICL2 binds to a pocket of hydrophobic residues between $\alpha 5$ and $\alpha\text{N}/\beta 1$ through F139^{ICL2}. This binding may liberate $\alpha 5$ from $\alpha\text{N}/\beta 1$, eventually triggering GDP release¹⁰. To simulate the release of GDP from the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate without a very invasive bias, we started a final set of MD simulations, in which we steered the C α -atom of F139^{ICL2} toward the C α -atom of F376 ^{$\alpha 5$} (**Methods**), followed by unbiased all-atom MD simulations (**Table S 1**). In the unbiased simulations, we observe breakage of the remaining contacts of GDP with G α , releasing Mg²⁺ bound GDP from its pocket (Figure 5A(III), **movie 5**). In agreement with previous radio-footprint labeling data¹⁰ binding of F139^{ICL2} to F376 ^{$\alpha 5$} further opens the interaction between $\alpha 5$ and the $\alpha\text{N}-\beta 1$ junction, followed by a more complete opening of $\alpha 1-\alpha\text{F}$, eventually triggering GDP release (**Figure 5B(III), Extended Data Fig 9, movie 5**). In this putative transient intermediate, the interaction between $\alpha 5$ and $\alpha\text{N}/\beta 1$ with ICL1 is substituted by ICL2, and G α rotates clockwise to adopt an orientation close to that observed in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ structure (Figure 5C(III)).

Discussion

Kinetic studies of G-protein activation have previously revealed that GDP dissociation, which enables GTP uptake, is the rate-determining step during G-protein activation^{50,51}. Along the path to nucleotide exchange, the first functional complex formed is an R-G^{GDP} intermediate^{22,10,52} (**Figure 1**). Using MD simulations, we have captured $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ states that can function as such intermediate. We show that the association of Gs^{GDP} with the $\beta_2\text{AR}$ leads to structural changes in G α , breakage of contacts of the switchI region with GDP, an opening of $\alpha 1-\alpha\text{F}$, displacement of αG and the opening of the α -helical domain, which significantly reduces the energy needed for GDP release (**Figure 4, Figure 5(II), Table S 5**). Transmission of the signal to the G protein involves receptor regions H8, ICL1, and TM2, which do not interact with the G protein in the crystal structure of the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ complex⁵. To reach the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ state, the G protein must still undergo an in-plane rotation against the receptor (**Figure 5(III,IV)**). Notably, a separate time-resolved cryo-EM study examining the stepwise mechanism of G-protein activation in response to GTP loading, found that the G protein undergoes an in-plane rotation against the receptor in the opposite direction during the dissociation process⁵³. When comparing the two processes, other similarities emerge and, in many aspects, structural changes induced in G α by binding to the receptor, which ultimately leads to the ejection of GDP, are reversed in order during G protein dissociation following GTP binding⁵³. In each case, the signal propagates in different directions. During association, the signal propagates from the receptor to the nucleotide-binding pocket. While after nucleotide exchange, the signal propagates again back to the receptor, leading to functional dissociation of the G protein from the receptor. In the case of the system studied here, the corkscrew-like binding and unbinding motion results in the interrogation of almost the entire receptor interface by the G protein, providing multiple opportunities for receptor discrimination between cognate and non-cognate

interactions. Central to this selection process are flexible structural elements of the receptor, such as TM6 and ICL2, that, together with disordered interface regions^{23,54}, tune the receptor's ability to bind and activate G proteins.

Declarations

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Author contributions:

H.B and G.P.H contributed equally sharing co-first authorship. H.B. refined initial models, performed MD simulations and data analysis, prepared figures, and wrote the initial draft. G.P.H. conceptualized and performed data analysis and prepared figures. M.S performed mutation experiments. J. K. S. T contributed to generation of the starting model and suggested mutations. R.G.G contributed to generation of the starting model. F. R provided sequence analysis. P.F.S supervised sequence analysis. P.S helped with development of the manuscript and figures. B.K.K and X.L provided initial structural data, suggested mutations and supervised mutation experiments. J.M.M designed and performed functional studies. P.W.H conceptualized the study, supervised the project and wrote the manuscript. All authors contributed to the proof-reading and final approval of the submitted version of the manuscript. H.B., G.P.H and P.W.H wrote the manuscript.

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Figures

Figure 1

Schematic representation of receptor engagement with the G-protein from first recognition till nucleotide exchange. Left: ligand-bound active state β_2 AR (R, in green) and inactive heterotrimeric G_s^{GDP} before association. The G_α -subunit is comprised of a Ras-like domain (Ras, orange) and α -helical domain (AHD, cyan). The G_β and G_γ subunits, in the background, are rendered in transparent violet and yellow, respectively. **Center:** Association of G_α^{GDP} with the receptor leads to the β_2 AR- G_s^{GDP} intermediate (this work). The $\alpha 5$ helix of G_α binds centrally to the intracellular binding pocket of the receptor, while the αN -helix of G_α binds laterally to H8. Intracellular loop 1 (ICL1) binds between $\alpha 5$ and αN . Binding of G_s^{GDP} to the β_2 AR is followed by long-range allosteric effects that reduce the energy needed for GDP (violet) release. In particular, the AHD opens, breaking GDP contacts. **Right:** Crystal structure of the β_2 AR- G_s^{empty}

complex, in which the G protein is rotated with respect to the receptor by ca. 40°, compared to the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (middle). In $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ the $\alpha 5$ helix binds more laterally to the intracellular binding pocket of the receptor and the ICL2 binds between $\alpha 5$ and αN . GTP (grey) binds to the open nucleotide binding pocket of $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ to activate the G protein in the next step⁵³.

Figure 2

Engagement of Gs protein with β_2 AR and long-range allosteric effects on nucleotide-binding pocket. A) Time-trace of β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} complex formation, monitored by the R131^{3.50}-E392 ^{α 5} distance from β_2 AR and Gs^{GDP}, respectively, in an example trajectory of the β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} simulations. Starting from a distance of more than 10 Å, an ionic interaction is formed between R131^{3.50}-E392 ^{α 5} (arrows indicate starting position and position when the ionic interaction forms). The 3D insets show the starting frame of Gs^{GDP} before association with β_2 AR (left), a sample snapshot from the β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} interface (middle) and, with a similar contact interface, the crystal structure of a β_2 AR- α 5-peptide complex¹⁶ (right) **(Extended Data Fig 1A3)**. **B)** Per-trajectory distributions of the R131^{3.50}-E392 ^{α 5} distance in all β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} simulations monitoring the establishment of that contact. **C)** Time-trace of the GDP-R201^{SwitchI} interaction, monitored by residue-residue distance in the same example trajectory in β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} (blue) and Gs^{GDP} (black), respectively **(Table S 1)**. **D)** Per-trajectory distributions of the GDP-R201^{SwitchI} distance in all β_2 AR-Gs^{GDP} and Gs^{GDP} simulations. **E)** Climbing of the TM6 lysine ladder by the carboxyl-terminus of L394 ^{α 5} and formation of the R131^{3.50}-E392 ^{α 5} ionic interaction, during the first 500 ns in the same example trajectory of Gs^{GDP} binding to β_2 AR. Shown is the surface of the receptor (green), the Ras (yellow) with GDP and the AHD (cyan), while G $\beta\gamma$ is omitted for clarity. Also shown as cylinders are the α 5 helix (orange) and TM6 (green).

Figure 3

Comparison of $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ and $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ interfaces. **A)** Heatmaps of the receptor interface from the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ simulations (left) and $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$ simulations (right) from previous work⁴⁵ (see **Table S 1** for an overview of MD simulations). The interface strength is computed as the number of residue contacts established between any receptor residues and any G-protein residues, averaged over the simulation time and aggregated to each individual residue (**Table S 2**). The comparison reveals an extended interface in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ simulations, including H8 and ICL1. For clarity, only αN , $\alpha\text{N-}\beta_1$, β_1 , and α_5 of $\text{G}\alpha$ are shown, while the rest of $\text{G}\alpha$, GDP and $\text{G}\beta\gamma$, are omitted. **B)** Potency of isoproterenol (ISO) on cAMP levels of FLAG-tagged WT $\beta_2\text{AR}$ or mutants expressed in triple knockout $\beta\text{arr}1/\beta\text{arr}2/\beta_2\text{AR}$ HEK293A cells. At two different expression levels, ISO potency was lower for $\beta_2\text{AR}$ mutants than WT. Data shown are from $n=7$ independent experiments (see also **Extended Data Fig 8** for cell surface expression levels, concentration response curves and isoprenaline affinities. **C)** Double-mutation sites shown as pairs of color-coded dots overlaid on $\beta_2\text{AR}$. The color code is the same as in B).

Figure 4

Structural changes in G_s^{GDP} in response to receptor association. **A)** Superposition of the four different G protein-states obtained from PCA analysis of pooled G_s^{GDP} and $\beta_2AR-G_s^{GDP}$ simulation data reveal substantial conformational changes in G_α in the $\beta_2AR-G_s^{GDP}$ intermediate (violet) compared to inactive G_s^{GDP} (orange). In the two states (magenta and cyan) connecting the inactive G_s^{GDP} state with the β_2AR-

Gs^{GDP} intermediate, the $\alpha 5/\alpha N-\beta 1$ scaffold is opening but the AHD remains closed. **B)** Comparison of inactive Gs^{GDP} (orange) and the intermediate $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ (violet) reveals rigid body motions of αN , $\beta 1$, $\alpha 4$, $\alpha 5$, αF and αG from Ras and displacement of the AHD, all of which rearrange the network of amino acids holding GDP in the nucleotide binding pocket. **C)** Overlay of 50 representative structures of the inactive Gs^{GDP} state (orange) and the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (violet). Ca-atoms of residues of the GDP binding pocket are represented as dots. Interactions that remain intact in the inactive Gs^{GDP} but not in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (violet) are highlighted in red. **D)** Left: Binding of $\alpha 5$ accompanying the kink at TM6 in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (deep green), but not in the connecting states (light green), where $\alpha 5$ is yet not fully engaged. The kink is stabilized when Y326^{7.53} from the NPxxY motif interacts with G280^{6.42} at the middle of TM6. Right: ICL2 adopts an α -helical conformation in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (deep green) promoting the F139^{ICL2} interaction with H362 ^{$\beta 6$} . **E)** Opening of the interaction between $\alpha 5$ and the $\alpha N-\beta 1$ junction in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (violet) allows F212 ^{$\beta 2$} to shift toward $\alpha 1$ through a rotamer switch. **F)** Left: Opening of the $\alpha 1$ and αF interaction in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (violet). Middle: Displacement of TCAT and αG in the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate (violet). Right: Opening of AHD in $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ (violet).

$\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ association

$\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{empty}}$

Figure 5

Overview of structural changes during Gs^{GDP} association with the receptor. From left to right: I) Gs^{GDP} (Ras, in orange, AHD in cyan and GDP in violet, $\text{G}\beta\gamma$ in transparent colors in the background) and $\beta_2\text{AR}$ (green) before coupling. II) Representative structure of the $\beta_2\text{AR-Gs}^{\text{GDP}}$ intermediate state. III) Representative snapshot after GDP release from its initial binding pocket as a result of steering ICL2

towards $\alpha 5$ and the αN - $\beta 1$ junction (**movie7**). **IV**) Crystal structure of the β_2AR - Gs^{empty} state (PDB ID: 3SN6). **A**) Side-view on the complexes shows the structural changes from Gs^{GDP} association with the receptor to the nucleotide-free state. **B**) Top view from the intracellular perspective highlights a progressive opening of αF - $\alpha 1$ and the AHD of $G\alpha$ during that process. $G\beta\gamma$ and receptor are omitted for clarity. **C**) View from the intracellular perspective indicates a clockwise rotational movement of the G-protein represented by αN , $\beta 1$, and $\alpha 5$ of $G\alpha$ relative to the receptor, from initial engagement to the nucleotide-free state.

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